

***EFL Teacher Professional Development Considerations: A Case study in
Different Schools of Cañar Province.***

***Consideraciones sobre el desarrollo profesional del docente de inglés: un
estudio de caso en diferentes escuelas de la provincia de Cañar***

Ariel Andrés Rivera Vásquez

Universidad Nacional de Educación

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6546-5606>

ariel.rivera@unae.edu.ec

Diana Alejandrina González Rivas

Ministerio Nacional de Educación

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-4361-4195>

RESUMEN

Esta investigación se ha centrado en conocer los criterios que tienen algunos profesores de lengua extranjera (inglés) en cuanto al Desarrollo Profesional Docente (DPD) conforme la motivación, la formación continua y la colaboración profesional. Por lo tanto, el objetivo de la investigación fue comprender estos aspectos desde las percepciones, experiencias y opiniones de los participantes. Veintidós profesores de inglés de diferentes escuelas de la provincia de Cañar participaron voluntariamente proporcionando datos e información. En el marco de este trabajo se adoptó un enfoque cualitativo centrado en un estudio de caso dentro de esta provincia con estos profesores de inglés. Además, se empleó una encuesta que fue validada por tres expertos antes de su implementación. Los datos recopilados fueron integrados y analizados de acuerdo con las tres dimensiones del DPD. Los hallazgos mostraron una actitud positiva hacia el DPD, donde la motivación de estos profesores tiende hacia mecanismos intrínsecos y la colaboración fue considerada beneficiosa bajo circunstancias específicas de respeto y cooperación entre ellos. Finalmente, las oportunidades de formación han sido escasas para ellos, en comparación con los profesores de otras áreas. Los participantes expresaron su preocupación por este escenario por lo cual solicitaron el aumento de los períodos académicos en la asignatura de inglés.

Palabras clave: *DPD, Colaboración, Motivación, Formación, Profesores de Inglés*

ABSTRACT

This research focused on how some EFL teachers perceived Teacher Professional Development (TPD) regarding motivation, training, and professional collaboration. The aim was to understand these aspects through the participants' perceptions, experiences, and opinions. Twenty-two EFL teachers from various schools in Cañar Province voluntarily provided data. The study adopted a qualitative approach, centered on a case study of these teachers within the province. A survey, validated by three experts prior to its implementation, was used to collect data. The findings were analyzed based on the three dimensions of TPD. The results revealed a positive attitude towards TPD, with teachers' motivation driven largely by intrinsic factors. Collaboration was considered beneficial under conditions of mutual respect and cooperation among colleagues. However, training opportunities were found to be limited compared to those available to teachers in other areas. The participants expressed concern about this disparity and requested an increase in the number of class periods for English language instruction.

Keywords: *TPD, Motivation, Collaboration, Training, EFL teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teacher professional development (TPD) has become fundamental in daily practice within the educational scope, considering the rapid changes that occur in society currently. Every day, pedagogical innovations and adaptations are needed to support learners' development of new capacities. According to Ayvaz and Çobanoğlu (2018), teacher professional development is mandatory and regulated by different decrees in some countries that establish active teacher participation in diverse training programs. Therefore, adequate mechanisms for access to high-quality training programs with enough pedagogical components to meet the changing needs of both current and future societies are mandatory.

Since the 2000s, Ecuador has been putting different tactics into practice through the Ministry of Education that are in line with ongoing training for teacher professional practice. According to Ponce (2010), the low and restricted effectiveness of learning in Latin American schools, particularly in Ecuador, compelled policymakers to strengthen and implement new laws intended to bolster the professional skills of teachers. The country has been working to raise the educational standard since 2006, as evidenced by the introduction of new initiatives like the Intercultural Education Law in 2011 and the ten-year Education Plan 2006–2015 (Fabara, 2013). In addition, there have been specific programs destined for teacher development, such as the “Integral System of Professional Educational Development” in 2008, “I am a teacher and I never stop learning” in 2014, and the platform “MECAPACITO” in 2016 (Castillo-Canales et al., 2022).

These nationwide training initiatives provided teachers with courses in different pedagogical areas, and the central aim has been to increase learning achievements in the Ecuadorian school system. In this regard, English Foreign Language (EFL) teachers are compelled to improve their professional skills, as well as the teacher of other disciplines. Additionally, EFL teachers must demonstrate at least a B2 level of proficiency in the target language as a mandatory requirement to be employed in public schools (Ministerio de Educación, 2025). Therefore, these educators require special attention and sustained support to maintain their language proficiency by acquiring updated pedagogical tools and knowledge.

As said before, some different nationwide programs offered by the Ministry of Education have been launched; however, those specific for EFL teachers could be the 2012 program called “GO TEACHER” that provided the possibility to develop English proficiency in the United States or the 2016 “Time to Teach” program that failed in the attempt to improve EFL teacher skills. Also, the 2019 “Ecuador habla inglés,” which is an agreement between the US Embassy and the Ministry of Education, and finally the “MECAPACTIO” platform (Chicaiza et al., 2023).

Despite the efforts made by the Ministry of Education, levels of English proficiency in the learners' population of the public system are still low and insufficient. De Angelis (2022) supports this statement showing the ranking of the EF EPI in 2021, which is an international test designed to measure English levels according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Ecuador is situated in the eighteenth position of twenty participant countries with a very low domain in the target language. This fact shows that something does not have the expected effect on the educational stage, and learners' achievements could be analyzed from different perspectives to understand what pedagogical and scholar elements are being misunderstood.

The current situation is not favorable for the school system, leading this research paper to pursue a deeper understanding of the problem and try to explain in more detail what the main constraints in EFL teaching are. Consequently, this study poses the following query: How is

perceived TPD for EFL teachers? This question demands intervention in school contexts by gathering information from EFL educators. For that reason, this study aims to understand the perspectives, opinions, and experiences of these EFL teachers at different schools in Cañar province about TPD.

There are three primary justifications for the development of this research: the first is the imperative need to understand some possible failures in TPD for EFL teachers. In such a manner, it is possible to clarify some constraints and problems, and even so, explanations about what necessities are demanded by teachers. The second is related to the prevalent low learning levels of EFL in students and how to mitigate it by an innovative approach considering teachers' necessities. And finally, the possibility of showing new paths of action where policymakers, district authorities, and school principals could elaborate on or plan new strategies to enhance the current problem in classrooms.

Furthermore, current literature on the TPD of EFL teachers in Ecuador fails to address crucial aspects such as motivation, training, and collaboration. For instance, the study by Vélez et al. (2025) focuses on how public policy influences EFL teacher performance, highlighting the need for greater attention, public investment, and clearer guidelines. Similarly, Cajas and Cherres (2024) aimed to measure the impact of introducing Lesson Study methodology into professional EFL teaching practice. In addition, Recino et al. (2020) conducted an exploratory study on teachers' competencies to better understand the low levels of English learning achievement, placing special emphasis on school infrastructure and public policy. In conclusion, this notable lack of information regarding EFL teachers' TPD justifies the present study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

EFL teaching in Ecuador

There has been an intriguing historical development of English language instruction in Ecuador. According to British Council (2015), the Curriculum Reform Aimed at the Development of the Learning of English, or CRADLE was a proposal made by the Ministry of Education and the British Council where English language was considered as a component of the mainstream education system inside curriculum design in 1992. The CARDLE proposal introduced several policy changes and new materials at the national level, but the anticipated impact on learning outcomes was not achieved. The minimal impact of CARDLE is supported by Ortega and Aucahuallpa (2017), as a result students who pursue higher education exhibit deficiencies in the English language despite their participation in the program.

In 2014, the ministerial agreement No. 0052-14 was launched indicating the obligation to include the English language in all levels of compulsory education (Ministerio Nacional de Educación, 2014). As mentioned before, various in-service training initiatives have been implemented for EFL teachers since 2012. In this sense, it is not plausible to deny the progress and positive outcomes achieved in EFL education, where the sense of instruction changes to student-centered teaching with more prepared educators (Cifuentes et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the international rankings of English levels in Ecuador are still under the curriculum standards, where the outcome is B1 level according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) at the final stage of baccalaureate (De Angelis, 2022; and Ministerio de Educación, 2016). The shortcomings in EFL attainments could vary across a wide spectrum of causes; however, in this research, the primary point of attention is TPD as a crucial resource for information on these constraints.

Teacher Professional Development (TPD)

TPD can be considered as an integrated approach to teaching professional career. According to Castillo-Canales et al. (2022) and Çetin and Bayrakçı (2019), TPD entails a series of planned, spontaneous, formal, and even informal situations where educators could improve and strengthen their professional knowledge and abilities, putting their intentions not only in individual growth but instead in collaborative participation of school agents leading to students' well-being and learning. Thus, TPD has positive influences on students' inclination for study, outcomes, motivation, and authentic interest (Ragusa and Levonisova, 2024).

The growth of new skills and the updating of previous ones seem like simple tasks to cover, but constant development needs a balance between the expectations of the teacher and the educational stage requirements. In short, TPD must reflect the current professional demands of teachers and learning standards in the educational system (Cambridge English Assessment, 2018; and Perry, 2022). The right contemplation of these elements probably could have the expected impact, and new innovations in EFL teaching would appear.

TPD could integrate several dimensions to study and analyze; nevertheless, in this paper, motivation, collaboration, and training will be the principals. According to Zhang et al. (2021), motivation has an undeniable effect on professional growth and a positive impact on students learning. On the other hand, from the contributions of Raj (2023), teacher training correlates with professional abilities, capacities, and productivity, which makes it a substantial dimension to be considered in TPD. Finally, collaboration and networking among professionals in education is another aspect that represents the active engagement among partners providing help to each other and sharing experiences that can be valuable in the TPD path (Chicaiza et al., 2023).

Motivation and TPD

Inside the human psyche, motivation is commonly defined as a set of forces and impulses that drive individuals to pursue objectives with enthusiasm and determination (Bandhu et al., 2024; Urhahne and Wijnia, 2023). This definition involves mechanisms that trigger people's inner resources, abilities, and skills during a long-term period. The focus and energy invested over time entail a predisposition in individuals, driven by the expectation of achieving a specific, pre-established goal. This construct is not only attributed to learning outcomes and student maturing but instead to teachers and TPD. As Avidov (2016) said, "the process of professional development takes place throughout the teachers' professional life; it is grounded in teachers' motivation and personal commitment" (p. 655).

In this line, teacher motivation maintains a close relationship with the improvement of pedagogical practices, planning and making decisions (Chiu et. al, 2021; and Lohbeck and Frenzel, 2022). These authors remark on the influence that motivation could have on teachers and students' performance as well as allowing them interact with tasks and demands in a more favorable and effective manner. If the teacher shows a positive attitude toward professional development, it is possible that motivation takes place at high levels inside that person (Fütterer et. al, 2023).

According to Tang et al. (2020), inner components and external factors could be determinants of the daily professional practice of teachers. In other words, this author refers to intrinsic and extrinsic types of motivation. As Bandhu et al. (2024) and Valdazan et al. (2024) said, intrinsic motivation encompasses internal triggered factors that are long-lasting and self-sustaining with their own personal interests, desires, and goals. Extrinsic motivation is determined by external influences such as personal pleasure, the avoidance of punishment,

economic rewards, social acceptance, and recognitions (Leagault, 2016; and Valdazan et al., 2024).

The difference between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation varies considerably, but from the assumptions of Lohbeck and Frenzel (2022) and Leagault (2016) intrinsic one is more desirable because it allows more enjoyment, better psychological well-being, more engagement and compromise. However, from the perspective of Nauman et al. (2021) extrinsic motivation affects teachers due to the importance of salary and benefits of their career covering their necessities. Teachers who are intrinsically motivated seek to increase their professional skills under a self-commitment where their responsibility leads them to improve their teaching practices, whereas extrinsic ones try to obtain some recognition, achieve higher degrees of education, and better economic conditions (Avidov, 2016). Additionally, different studies made by the collaboration of novel and experienced teachers show that motivation can vary and those with years of in-service practice are less inclined to grow their professional repertoire than novice teachers (Zhang et al., 2021).

Training and TPD

Teachers' continuous involvement in training programs constitutes another key aspect to predict progress in learning achievements of students (Dhari et al., 2023). In depth, all kinds of programs, courses, seminars, or similar activities guide education processes to meet current demands that society requests. For Kandel and Kandel (2023), training entails maturing in procedure skills and knowledge in specific areas. In education, particularly, training programs supply better pedagogical tools and deeper understanding of classroom mechanisms.

Teacher training could be seen as an effective strategy for conveying more quality in education stage. Nauman et al. (2021) support the benefits that continuous training carries; moreover, they instigate teachers to create collaborative contributions among them. However, Reisoğlu (2021) recommends the accurate implementation of these programs acknowledging that fail is possible because they do not bridge conceptual instrumentation with real school requirements. Cambridge English Assessment (2018) indicates the urgency of providing teachers sustained support offering them enough opportunities to engage in training programs proposed.

Training programs should not be allocated only for a few, instead, these could be accessible for everyone from a democratic perspective. In doing so, information and communication technologies (ICT) emerge to democratize knowledge access with new development chances. For Castillo-Canales et al. (2022), ICT could impact teachers by Massive Online Open Courses (MOOCs), benefiting the entire system, reducing costs of implementation, and making TPD a sustainable option.

Collaboration and TPD

Collaboration is defined as the interaction and support of peers seeking a common goal; it also improves professional bonds and trustworthiness among people (Dahal, 2023). Collaborative engagement among teachers is a driving force to share and complement the colleagues' growth by taking part in the planning, implementation, and assessment of different proposals and continuous learning (Bergmark, 2023). Therefore, collaboration is fundamental in TPD due to the positive influence that teachers can have on one another. This influence occurs by sharing their efforts, learning gains and professional amendments. In sum, they are part of significant goals that exceed individualism and achieve bigger results in learners' education.

METHOD

The current research was focused on perceptions and experiences that EFL teachers have had in reference to their professional development from the opportunities, constraints, and future recommendations to increase achievements in the English language subject. In that perspective, a qualitative approach entails the appropriate characteristics to explore and obtain significant data. Ponce et al. (2022) define qualitative research as a well-established path to grasp educational components since it has a flexible scope that captures deep social, cultural, and moral aspects. Thus, the qualitative research lens fits the aim and conditions of the study.

The specific type of research in this work was a case study, which aligns with a qualitative approach and has distinct characteristics. According to Tomaszewski et al. (2020) and Canta and Quesada (2011) case studies are part of qualitative research and establish the comprehension of a contemporary phenomenon in real contexts under specific boundaries. In other words, the case study investigates a particularity defined by the conditions of the research. The specific case in this research was delimited inside Cañar province and EFL teachers' perceptions.

Participants

These were twenty-two EFL teachers from different schools in Cañar province, who participated actively and voluntarily in the study. Their identities were kept secret, maintaining the principle of anonymity and confidentiality. Their opinions and experiences about TPD vary greatly depending on the person, but they have in common the same concern that moves them to grow as professionals who want to bolster learning outcomes.

Analyses

The research instrument employed was the survey. Prior to its implementation, this instrument was validated by three experts (university professors). The validation process utilized a structured rubric to evaluate several key aspects. One of these aspects was suitability, where three aspects were considered: Comprehensibility of questions (clarity, preciseness, unambiguity), the appropriateness of response options; and the logical sequence of questions. Additionally, the relevance was another aspect examined by the experts; here they observed: The pertinence of each question to the study's objectives and the alignment of questions with the core dimensions of TPD (collaboration, training, and motivation). At the end, the three experts make suggestions and changes that were added for the subsequent approval, consequently, one additional question was appended at the end of the instrument to enhance its comprehensiveness and relevance.

The survey included introductory questions, followed by others focused on motivation, collaboration, and training programs as key dimensions of Teacher Professional Development (TPD). It concluded with two closing questions. The instrument was distributed to various public schools in Cañar via Google Forms. The collected responses were analyzed using Atlas.ti (free version), a qualitative research software. The data were triangulated across the three TPD categories—motivation, collaboration, and training—and graphical representations were created using Draw.io (free version).

RESULTS

At the beginning of the survey, participants were required to answer two introductory questions to gain a focused perspective on the importance of TPD and its key components. The answers that participants shared were, in some cases, in Spanish language or English language, because some of them prefer to give information in one of these languages. In figure 1, it is

possible to visualize the main dimensions and reasons that EFL teachers are exposed to in relation to TPD.

Figure 1. TPD's dimensions and importance

EFL teachers' feedback on the value of TPD may be categorized into three distinct categories: improving student outcomes, professional development, and quality in education. Teachers paid attention to educational quality in this regard, and they had the following opinions to share: “los maestros deben capacitarse día a día para una enseñanza de calidad” – “Para mejorar la calidad educativa” – “To improve the English teaching process”- “Para mejorar el proceso de aprendizaje de los estudiantes” - “El uso de didácticas y metodologías que ayuden adaptarse a los cambios que sugieren en cada una de las aulas”. These opinions can be summarized as the attempts of these professionals to contribute to English Language Teaching (ELT) and learners's development where quality of education represents continuous training and efforts to gather new teaching knowledge.

About the improvement of learning outcomes as justification of TPD, there are some expressions that teachers used: “Para mejorar las competencias de los estudiantes” -- “Es la clave para mejorar la calidad de la enseñanza impactando positivamente en el aprendizaje de los estudiantes” – “Help to improve the teaching-learning process of the students” – “Un docente bien preparado no solo es más competente, sino que contribuye al éxito de nuestros estudiantes”. In this regard, the participants consider TPD to impact on learners, making their learning process effective and suitable.

Another point to consider is teacher development, because some participants reflect upon it concluding that teacher continuous training is the key for learning achievements and educational quality. In this sense can be cited the most relevant opinions: “We as English teachers must be in constant training, learning new techniques and strategies to apply in the class” – “It enables teachers to enhance their instructional methods” – “Para tener nuevos métodos y técnicas e irnos actualizando para enseñar”.

In sum, TPD is justified by the positive effect it has on learners, the teaching and learning process, and on the teacher's own development. We should consider the dimensions that integrate TPD for these reasons, and considering the teachers' opinions, the following three were chosen: training, collaboration and inner components of teachers.

The question number two delves into the most important ingredient for TPD. A considerable part of the data reveals that self-determination is the key. Some of their

expressions were: “Creativity, patience, dedication to work and love for students”- “The most important ingredient to enhance teacher professional development is reflection, as it enables teachers to examine their practices and beliefs” – “The teacher needs to feel motivated by constant innovation and for the benefit of students”.

Although there are many aspects of self-determination to check, the motivational component has been selected for this study. Question three seeks to understand whether teachers are motivated or not to engage in TPD. The following answer sums up in detail the feelings of most participants:

Yes, I am motivated to improve my teaching skills and knowledge because I believe that education is a constantly evolving field, and I must stay updated on best practices, new technologies, and innovative methods to provide high-quality instruction and support to my students, ultimately enhancing their learning outcomes and academic success.

This answer reflects most opinions, nevertheless it is also necessary to contemplate opposite perspectives. One participant conveys the following comment saying that he is not motivated because: “No, al ser un docente contratado el sueldo no cubre las necesidades básicas”. This sentence reveals the difference between those permanent appointments, and the others whose working conditions are not the same. Figure 2 shows different tendencies among teachers for extrinsic and intrinsic motivation.

Figure 2. Extrinsic and Intrinsic motivational indicators for TPD

Figure 2 summarizes the answers to question four, where teachers have five options about what motivates them to TPD. They tended to focus on the improvement of teaching skills and a better understanding of English language teaching methods, where intrinsic motivation was reported by nineteen participants. On the other hand, the rest of them showed external motivation related to the social-economic impact of TPD. From these perspectives, inner reasons have a greater preponderance than external, although, it is undeniable that salary and economic benefits are necessary and therefore should not go unnoticed.

The two following questions of the survey were designed to grasp collaboration as a fundamental part of TPD. In this particular instance, for example, it can be affirmed that collaboration determines the success of TPD, while the information is summarized in figure 3.

Figure 3. The Role of Collaboration in TPD

Some of the data corroborates this statement: “Nos ayuda a conocer la perspectiva y forma de enseñanza de los otros docentes del área de inglés”- “Sí, de manera positiva en la retroalimentación de pares para una mejora continua” – “It improves practice as it allows pedagogical actions to be coordinated, which generates a common line of work for the benefits of students” – “It helps to take risks by experimenting with new approaches and examining what does and does not work in different contexts”. The following comment gathers a profound reflection about that:

Collaboration among EFL teachers has a profoundly significant impact on teacher professional development, as working together enables them to share knowledge, ideas, and expertise, leading to improved teaching methods and practices, increased confidence and motivation, enhanced problem-solving and support, exposure to new perspectives and approaches, and development of leadership and communication skills, ultimately resulting in more effective teaching and better student outcomes.

Thus, collaboration can be considered part of TPD because it allows the development of skills related to communication and teaching abilities, which in turn affect learners’ education through coordinated planning. However, these participants made some suggestions about how to manage work among professionals: “I think a collaborative job can positively impact if the colleagues pursue the same goal” – “La colaboración entre colegas es muy buena siempre que sea en un ambiente de respeto y crítica constructiva”. Collaboration does not guarantee success, it requires the predisposition of the teachers to work in a respectful environment pursuing the same objectives. The final dimension to be considered is training. Figure 4 represents the elements that training has in regard to TPD.

Question number seven tries to deepen in training programs as opportunities for TPD, in that sense, participants remark them as invaluable chances for their growing as professionals. Some of these opinions about training are: “Con los programas nos actualizamos y desarrollamos nuestras habilidades” - “I think that this kind of programs are great opportunities to change” - “training programs are valuable opportunities to improve teacher capabilities, as they provide a structured environment to acquire new skills, knowledge, and methodologies”.

Figure 4. The role of training in TPD

Besides, question number eight seeks to identify if training programs cover their expectations, and they responded in this manner: “sí me ha ayudado a conocer sobre metodologías, especialmente digitales si me han ayudado para aplicar en el área de inglés sobre todo cuando estamos con estudiantes necesidades educativas especiales (NEE)” – “ Yes, they've equipped me with innovative teaching methodologies, enhanced my knowledge of language acquisition theories, and provided me with practical tools and resources to design engaging lessons, assess student progress, and differentiate instruction” – “No siempre encuentro cursos enfocados en la enseñanza de inglés”. The last comment reveals that English likely does not have the same impact as courses in other subjects.

Finally, question number nine looks into the support provided by Ministry of Education and the answers were: “En realidad los docentes de inglés no tenemos oportunidades de capacitarnos o consideran a los maestros con nombramiento definitivo, son muy pocas las puertas abiertas para los docentes” – “Bueno, pero al ser docente contratado, no existe una pariedad” – “El desarrollo profesional del MINEDUC es una oportunidad muy amplia que nos forman como docentes y tiene muchas áreas de gran interés, pero lastimosamente en cuanto a inglés ha existido una nula formación o capacitación para los docentes” – “It’s not ideal— English teachers always come last in every program.” – “There are not courses for English Teachers”.

This situation reveals, as said in the last paragraph, that EFL teaching has not received proper support from the Ministry. 58% of teachers openly stated that the Ministry has likely failed to address their needs, and even more concerning are the unequal conditions between contract workers and those with permanent appointments. This could be a singular issue to deepen in more detail, trying to reveal its real impact on professional development, and how this affects the quality of EFL education.

The ending question reflects upon the biggest challenge in English teaching and TPD and they said: “Staying current with the latest methodologies, technologies, and materials while adapting to individual students' needs and overcoming resource and time constraints” –

“Develop our students’ skills in Just 3 hours a week” – “Break schemes and work more hours in English since 3 is usually not enough”. The biggest problem seems to be the short amount of time, because students require more time in contact with English language to accomplish with demands of some specific levels according to CEFR.

DISCUSSION

Regarding the stance of Castillo-Canales et al. (2022); Çetin and Bayrakçı (2019); and Ragusa and Levonisova (2024), TPD could be considered crucial for better learning outcomes, affecting the professional performance of EFL teachers in a positive perspective and in turn increasing learning achievements in students. This idea is plenty confirmed by the twenty-two participants who consider TPD, in some cases, an obligation to fulfill students and society's needs, giving greater quality to educational processes, reinforcing their previous professional abilities, and developing new ones.

Motivation is one of the dimensions considered in the analysis; although the participants mentioned other inner components such as creativity, patience, dedication, and reflection, the study only covered intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Bandhu et al. (2024) and Urhahne and Wijnia (2023) define motivation as the mechanisms that trigger the impulse to achieve a goal. Due to such circumstances, the participants were asked if they are motivated to engage in TPD; the answers were positive; however, there was an answer that neglects motivation toward TPD. They also showed their interest in pursuing TPD, and 90% of them showed a tendency towards intrinsic motivation, and the other 10 % extrinsic motivation. Lohbeck and Frenzel (2022) and Leagault (2016) advocate intrinsic motivation because of their positive effects on people, but extrinsic motivation is not substandard, because socio-economic impacts could be understood to meet the basic needs of Life, as Nauman et al. (2021) claim.

Collaboration as a source of TPD, according to Dahal (2023) and Bergmark (2023) increases teaching skills by sharing ideas, experiences, improving interpersonal relationships by making learning process more coordinated. In this sense, the participants agreed and confirmed these ideas, recommending respect as an essential part of collaboration. Finally, Training was perceived how the key element to gain knowledge and upgrade skills.

Collaboration is defined as the interaction and support of peers seeking a common goal; it also improves professional bonds and trustworthiness among people (Dahal, 2023). Collaborative engagement among teachers is a driving force to share and complement the colleagues' growth by taking part in the planning, implementation, and assessment of different proposals and continuous learning (Bergmark, 2023). Therefore, collaboration is part of TPD due to the influence that one teacher could have on another, and by sharing their efforts, learning gains and professional amendments are part of significant goals that exceed individualism and achieve bigger results in learners' education as Kandel and Kandel (2023) and Nauman et al. (2021) argue. However, despite the historical review of Cifuentes et al. (2019), about the different nationwide programs launched for EFL teachers since 2012, the participants stated that there had not been courses for them as EFL teachers, making these situations of inequality. Considering that Me CAPCITO curses offered a variety of training of other subjects, English has been not considered. The participants also shared their ideas about the biggest challenge for English teaching language, and most part of them agreed in the limited amount of time to work per week, three-hour class is not enough to meet quality standards.

Finally, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The 22 participants represent a small group of EFL teachers; although their knowledge and reflections constitute a rich source of information, additional volunteer participation will be necessary. In this vein, involving a broader pool of EFL teachers would provide more comprehensive data, while simultaneously avoiding potential biases in the interpretation of results. Nevertheless, this study addresses TPD from a fresh perspective, as previous research—such as Vélez et al. (2025), Cajas and Cherres (2024), and Recino et al. (2020)—has primarily focused on public policy, infrastructure, and lesson study methodology.

CONCLUSIONS

This study focused on exploring how EFL teachers perceive TPD based on their opinions and experiences. As noted here, motivation, collaboration, and training have been the dimensions of analysis. Regarding motivation, the results show a clear tendency in teachers who participated in the study to engage in different activities related to TPD. In more detail, these teachers showed intrinsic motivation, trying to evolve as professionals to impact learners' education, although a smaller part of them demonstrated extrinsic motivation about economic benefits. Collaboration is another aspect that was contemplated as a foundational part of TPD; however, the results point out that its effectiveness lies in an environment of respect towards a common goal. For its part, training is recognized as an opportunity to gain new skills in teaching; however, the opinions demonstrate the lack of courses and activities for English subject. This situation could be analyzed in more detail, trying to comprehend the reasons and consequences that the lack of training and support represents for EFL teachers.

Regarding the limitations of this study, future research should involve a larger sample of EFL teachers, as 22 participants still represent a limited group. With broader representation, findings would be more robust and less susceptible to potential biases. Overall, it is strongly recommended to conduct further research on TPD and EFL teachers, as the current scarcity of studies may obscure key challenges and needs within this teaching community. It is crucial to amplify their voices and reflections through scientific literature.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Ariel Andrés Rivera Vásquez: Conducted the preliminary bibliographical research and co-wrote the introduction, literature review, methodology, data collection, discussion, and conclusions.

Diana Alejandrina González: Conducted the preliminary bibliographical research and co-wrote the introduction, literature review, methodology, data collection, discussion, and conclusions.

ETHICAL IMPLICATION

The authors declare that there are no ethical implications associated with this study.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no financial or non-financial conflicts of interest that could have influenced the work presented in this article.

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES

- Avidov, O. (2016) A model of professional development: teachers' perceptions of their professional development. *Teachers and Teaching*, 22, (6), 653-669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2016.1158955>
- Ayvaz, Z., and Çobanoğlu, F. (2018). In-service teacher training: Problems of the teachers as learners. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(4), 159-174. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1191719>
- Bandhu, D., Murali, M., Prashant, N., Jadhav, P., Bhadauria, A., and Saxena, K. (2024). Theories of motivation: A comprehensive analysis of human behavior drivers. *Acta Psychologica*, 244, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104177>
- Bergmark, U. (2020). Teachers' professional learning when building a research-based education: context-specific, collaborative and teacher-driven professional development. *Professional Development in Education*, 49(2), 210–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2020.1827011>
- Brandão, A., Pedro, L., and Zagalo, N. (2024). Teacher professional development for a future with generative artificial intelligence – an integrative literature review. *Digital Education Review*, (45), 150-158. <https://doi.org/10.1344/der.2024.45.151-157>
- British Council. (2015). *English in Ecuador an examination of policy, perceptions and influencing factors*. <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/sites/teacheng/files/English%20in%20Ecuador.pdf>
- Cajas, D., and Cherras, K. (2024). Challenges and opportunities of using lesson study in English language teaching among Ecuadorian EFL teachers. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 7(23), 525-538. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.23.7.26>
- Cambridge Assessment English. (2018). *The Cambridge assessment English approach to teacher professional development*. <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/Images/539683-perspectives-teacher-professional-development.pdf>
- Castillo-Canales, D., Mancilla, A., Restrepo, R., Martínez, F. (2022). *Teacher professional development supported by information and communication technologies: A case study of the “Teacher Training Program for Curricular Update 2016-2018 in Ecuador”*. Foundation for Information Technology Education and Development. <https://shorturl.at/xACjS>

- Çetin, C., and Bayrakçı, M. (2019). Teacher Professional Development models for effective teaching and learning in schools. *The Online Journal of Quality in Higher Education*, 6 (1), 32-38. <https://tojkih.net/journals/tojkih/articles/v06i01/v06i01-04.pdf>
- Chicaiza, V., Encalada, E., Sarah, I, Jordan, C., and Romero, V. (2023). Teacher professional development: Connecting the past, present, and future. In Newman, S.J., Gibson, S.T., Cajás, D. and Acosta, H. (Eds.), *English language education in Ecuador: Assessing opportunities for teaching and learning in a developing nation* (pp. 74-92). USFQ PRESS. <https://www.dspace.uce.edu.ec/server/api/core/bitstreams/5c2c9945-2a63-4a40-933c-165758f857ce/content>
- Chiu, T., Chai, C., Williams, P., and Lin, T.-J. (2021). Teacher professional development on self-determination theory–based design thinking in STEM education. *Educational Technology & Society*, 24 (4), 153–165. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48629252>
- Cifuentes, M., Contreras, R., and Beltrán, M. (2019). The development of the English language teaching in the high schools of Ecuador during the last two decades. *Polo del Conocimiento*, 4(10), 89-98. <https://polodelconocimiento.com/ojs/index.php/es/article/view/1159>
- Dahri, N., Al-Rahmi, W., Almogren, A., Yahaya, N., Vighio, M., and Al-Maatuok, Q. (2023). Mobile-based training and certification framework for teachers’ professional development. *Sustainability* 15, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15075839>
- Dahal, G. (2023). Collaborative mentoring for in-service teachers’ well-being in the nepalese context. *Journal of NELTA Gandaki*, 6(1-2), 89–97. <https://tinyurl.com/3r76rh7d>
- De Angelis, A. (2022). EF English proficiency index e inglés en Ecuador: Suposiciones inciertas del ranking internacional. *Revista Andina De Educación*, 5(2), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.32719/26312816.2022.5.2.11>
- Fabara, E. (2013). *Estado del arte de la formación docente en el Ecuador*. La Caracola Editores. <https://contratosocialecuador.org/images/publicaciones/cuadernos/8.pdf>
- Fütterer, T., Ritcher, E., and Ritcher, D. (2023). Teachers’ engagement in online professional development—the interplay of online professional development quality and teacher motivation. *Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaft*, 27, 739–768. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11618-024-01241-8>
- Kandel, R., and Kandel, G. (2023). Collaboration, discussion, and feedback for improving students’ (report) writing and presentation: A participatory action research. *Journal of NELTA Gandaki*, 6(1-2), 26–38. <https://tinyurl.com/ywnj3wzr>

- Leagult, L. (2016). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. *Springer International Publishing*, 1-4.
https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-3-319-28099-8_1139-1
- Lohbeck, A., and Frenzel, A. (2022). Latent motivation profiles for choosing teaching as a career: How are they linked to self-concept concerning teaching subjects and emotions during teacher education training? *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 92(1), 37–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12437>
- Ministerio de Educación del Ecuador. (2014). Acuerdo ministerial No. 0052-14: Inclusión obligatoria del idioma inglés en todos los niveles de educación obligatoria.
<https://shorturl.at/jyRc6>
- Ministerio de Educación. (2016). *Estándares curriculares o de aprendizaje área de inglés*.
<https://educacion.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2022/05/Estandares-Aprendizaje-Ingles.pdf>
- Ministerio de Educación. (2025). *Lineamientos para la selección de docentes – Educa Empleo*.
<https://educacion.gob.ec/wp-content/uploads/downloads/2025/07/lineamientos-educa-empleo-julio-2025.pdf>
- Nauman, H., Pasha, A., and Munawar. M. (2021). The role of teacher training programs in optimizing teacher motivation and professional development skills. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 43 (2) ,17-37. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1338294>
- Ortega, D., and Aucahuallpa, R. (2017). La educación ecuatoriana en inglés: Nivel de dominio y competencias lingüísticas de los estudiantes rurales. *Revista Científica*, 2(6), 52–73.
<https://doi.org/10.29394/scientific.issn.2542-2987.2017.2.6.3.52-73>
- Perry, E. (2023). Teacher professional development in changing circumstances: The impact of covid-19 on schools’ approaches to professional development. *Education Sciences*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13010048>
- Ponce, J. (2010). *Políticas educativas y desempeño: una evaluación de impacto de programas educativos focalizados en Ecuador*. FLACSO.
<https://biblio.flacsoandes.edu.ec/libros/118699-opac>
- Ponce, O., Gómez-Galán, J. and Pagán-Maldonado, N. (2022). Investigación cualitativa en educación: reexaminando sus teorías, prácticas y desarrollos en una era científico-política. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, (18), 278-295.
<https://doi.org/10.46661/ijeri.5917>
- Ragusa, G., Huang, S., and Levonisova, S. (2024). Middle school mathematics achievement: Effects of math teacher professional development. *International Journal of Teacher*

- Education and Professional Development*, 7(1), 1-37.
<https://doi.org/10.4018/IJTEPD.337965>
- Raj, G. (2023). Teacher training as a strategy of professional development: Perceptions and challenges. *Journal of NELTA-GADAKI*, 6(2),98-108.
<https://doi.org/10.3126/jong.v6i1-2.59716>
- Recino, U., Sevy, J., and Muñoz, C. (2020). Factors affecting English language teaching in public schools in Ecuador. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 3(19), 276-294.
<https://www.ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter/article/view/1948>
- Reisoğlu, İ. (2022). How does digital competence training affect teachers' professional development and activities? *Tech Know Learn* 27, 721–748.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-021-09501-w>
- Tang, S., Wong, A., Li, D., and Cheng, M. (2020). Millennial generation preservice teachers' intrinsic motivation to become a teacher, professional learning and professional competence. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 96, 1-12.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103180>
- Tomaszewski, L., Zarestky, J., and Gonzalez, E. (2020). Planning qualitative research: Design and decision making for new researchers. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920967174>
- Urhahne, D., and Wijnia, L. (2023). Theories of motivation in education: An integrative framework. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(45),1-35.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-023-09767-9>
- Valdazan, E., Caramato, A., Dionisio, J., Dionesio, M., Galangey, I., and Pasion, M. (2024). Extrinsic and intrinsic motivation and academic performance of pupils at quezon district public elementary schools. *Cognizance Journal*, 4(5), 54-66.
<https://cognizancejournal.com/vol4issue5/V4I505.pdf>
- Vélez, C., Rodríguez, H., Pesantez, A., and Zambrano, F. (2025). Desafíos y oportunidades en la formación continua de profesores de inglés en el sistema educativo ecuatoriano. *Código Científico revista de Investigación*, 6(1), 2369–2386.
<https://doi.org/10.55813/gaea/ccri/v6/nE1/821>
- Zhang, X., Admiraal, W., and Saab, N. (2021). Teachers' motivation to participate in continuous professional development: relationship with factors at the personal and school level. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 47(5), 714–731.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2021.1942804>